

Exploring ways we can investigate
Big Questions about ourselves
and the world around us

Why does life exist?

Let's investigate by thinking about the ways we try to understand how the world around us 'works'.

1 If we were to place inside this jar all the ingredients needed for life to exist on planet Earth, what would we add?

2 When we observe living things around us, we can learn about the relationships between different biological systems. We may wonder what happens to living things when there are changes in the environment.

3 Sometimes we might find there are questions that are hard to answer... for example "which came first – the chicken or the egg?"

4 One of the key relationships we can observe in the world around us is based on 'cause' and 'effect'. Look at the example of these dominoes... each one appears to be having an effect on the next one.

Think about what may be a 'cause' and an 'effect' for each of the following events:

- rain
- sunburn
- flowering
- falling

5 Imagine you are walking near the sea and you observe, in the sandy soil, fossilised remains of an animal that lived a long time ago. What kinds of questions might you ask about this animal?

7 Tina is a scientist at Diamond Light Source who uses the synchrotron to research questions about the structures and relationships of materials inside living things. Tina has helped to find out more about what happened to dinosaurs long ago by observing the structures inside fossils.

6 What challenges might you face when trying to find answers to some of these questions?

In this zine we will...

...be exploring the work of scientists who observe and seek to understand what is needed for life on Earth to exist and thrive

...find out how and why scientists at Diamond can work with paleontologists and geographers to explore events from a long time ago

...wonder about the ways we can investigate questions that help us build our knowledge about the world around us.

7 When building our knowledge about the past, it's useful to work with a timeline...

8 Are there more questions people may have about this timeline?

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What caused dinosaurs to become extinct?

Why do things change?

Paleontologists have developed a theory that some huge event must have caused the conditions on Earth to change so that dinosaurs could no longer survive. One theory is that an asteroid, the size of one of Earth's tallest mountains, crashed on to the Earth's surface.

When Mary Anning was 12 years old, she discovered a fossil of a creature that was different to the kinds of animals people saw around them. Eventually a new word needed to be created to name the animals we now call dinosaurs.

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What can help me know more about life that existed long ago if these living beings no longer exist?

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The artist Detlev van Ravenswaay has created this painting showing the size of the crater

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Although no humans were there to witness it, the place where the meteor landed left a huge 'footprint' on the surface of the Earth.

Tina was given a puzzle to try and solve... could she find evidence in a fossil that linked the death of dinosaurs to this meteor that crashed on Earth?

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Key words

Particle a very small piece of matter

X-Ray this form of light cannot be seen or felt – it is powerful enough to pass through most things, and is used to find out more about the structure of matter

Synchrotron works like a giant microscope, using the power of electrons to produce bright light (x-rays) that scientists can use to study anything from fossils to jet engines to viruses and vaccines

Scholar a scholar is like an investigator, studying an area of knowledge in detail to try and understand more about our world and its complex puzzles

Paleontologist a person who studies the history of life on Earth through fossils of plants and animals that lived up to billions of years ago

Fossil a part (or impression) of a living organism (an insect, animal or plant) that has been preserved in rock

Scientist Profile: Tina

When I was a child, my parents did not work in science, but shared their interest in scientific things with me

I was inspired by a teacher who shared with me stories through a scientific lens. These helped me to see a world full of wonder, and I went on to study physics

As part of my research I investigate what happens in living cells, and what is needed to help us be healthy

I have to learned that I need to keep an open mind when I am working in science research so that I can observe things that may be different to what I was looking for

Electromagnetic Spectrum

How did light help Tina to find out more about the past using fossils? ...

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The high energy X-ray beam travelled through the beamline - Tina used this to compare and identify structures of particles inside a tiny sample of the fossilised leg of a thescelosaurus.

Tina and other researchers use instruments to help their observations

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A magnifying glass uses **visible light** to help us observe small things.

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Why does a doctor use an X-ray when checking to see if a bone has been broken?

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Like finding a missing piece from a puzzle, Tina worked with a team to find evidence that a meteor caused a huge explosion, affecting all life on Earth at that time!

Paleontologists wanted to look for very small particles **inside** the fossil of a dinosaur's leg... without damaging it!

Using the X-ray beam from the synchrotron, Tina identified tiny particles from the meteor deep inside the fossil. The fossil had been discovered here... the meteor particles had been blasted over 3000 km north of the crash site!

Deep inside the fossilised leg were particles from the meteor...

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After the meteor crashed onto the Earth's surface, the sky was filled with dust, ash, and smoke. This spread and created a thick layer, like the darkest clouds, that stopped most of the light from the sun reaching plants. Why would this have affected many living creatures?

Which kinds of life could have survived years in dark and cold conditions?

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Meteor crater in the Gulf of Mexico

Thinking like a biologist - what other changes in the environment and growing conditions might affect plants?

Observe, Compare, Record

Scientists like Tina understand that it is important to find and check evidence to be able to say they 'know' something.

"Plants need light to thrive."

How do you know if this statement is true?

Thinking like a scientist would involve observing how and where plants grow and thrive. Imagine you are putting on your 'scientist hat'... look outside and observe the places where most plants seem to grow well.

What is the soil like - wet? dry? Is the season cold or warm?

Compare the same kinds of plants that are growing in light places to ones that are in darker places.

What could you do to test how important sunlight is for plants to thrive?

Hint - you may need to have an experiment that takes more than a few days... it may take some time to observe changes.

- 1) Take three containers (make sure each has a hole in the bottom), fill each with seedlings or a small leafy houseplant (like a spider plant)
- 2) Place each container on a small plate or saucer and move them to different places: one container in full sunlight (on a window sill), one in a place that is light but does not get full sunlight, and the last container somewhere very dark (maybe behind a cupboard or in a closed box).

- 1) Check that each container gets some water regularly (not too wet and not too dry).

At the end of the first week, put the containers side by side to compare what is happening to the plants. You could put the containers back and compare them at the end of the second week of your experiment.

At the end of the experiment, what can you say that you now know?

Find out more about:

- Research at Diamond Light Source through their website page 'Dinosaur CSI'
- Mary Anning through books and films (add to your search 'a fossil hunter's story', and 'sea dragon')
- David Attenborough's BBC documentaries about 'Sea Dragon' and 'Dinosaurs: the Final Day'

DISCIPLINARY
HAT ACTIVITY

a Wisdom involves being able to build and use our knowledge skilfully.

b When exploring the relationships between events and their causes, scientists and other scholars often find their discoveries lead to more questions about the world around us.

d When I am thinking with my 'scientist hat' on, what tools might I use to investigate possible answers to questions about the world?

c If I am 'thinking like a scientist', what kinds of questions might I want to ask? These might include 'how', 'what', 'when', and 'why' questions.

e If I am 'thinking like a historian' what kinds of questions might I want to ask? These might include 'when', 'what', 'why', and 'who' questions.

g How might artists help scientists and historians when trying to picture and understand more about past events?

f When I am thinking with my 'historian hat' on, what might I use to investigate possible answers to questions about the past?

i Big Questions are questions that explore being human and the world around us.

What Big Questions interest you?

'Thinking like a scholar' Activity
This is a 'Discipline Wheel' – it includes some examples of 'ways of knowing' (disciplines). Using this tool enables us to use more than one discipline ('way of knowing'), and helps us explore questions and puzzles about being human and the world around us. Investigate the Big Question in the middle using some of these different 'ways of knowing' (disciplines)?

h A scholar is a person who studies an area of knowledge in detail and depth.

Scholars from different disciplines can help each other investigate and try to develop good answers to complex questions, puzzles and problems!

For more info contact lasar@canterbury.ac.uk

The Power of Light

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